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The Connection Between Language and Culture (on the Example of The Compliment Concept in German and Uzbek Languages)

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Abstract : This article explains the connection between language and culture through fixed expressions, proverbs, and idiomatic phrases in the linguistic structure of intercultural communication between Germans and Uzbeks from a linguocultural and cognitive perspective. Furthermore, the article provides a comparative analysis of the actual scientific-theoretical issues and research tasks in the field of linguo-cultural studies within linguistics. It focuses on the qualities of the compliment concept in the speech culture of Germans and Uzbeks.

Key words : compliment concept, linguo-culturology, sociolinguistics, intercultural communication, pragmatic feature, paralinguistics, cognitive linguistics, comparative method, lexicography.

1 Introduction

In modern linguistics, the practice of systematically studying the factors that directly and indirectly influence the selection of linguistic phenomena in speech communication based on a comparative approach is gaining widespread importance. This study, as part of comparative linguistics, focuses on the description, derivation, inventory, and lexical-semantic classification of adjectives denoting human characteristics in the German and Uzbek languages. It also examines their semantic-syntactic potential (valency), functions in nominative word combinations, pragmatic features in the communication process, and their application in intercultural communication (compliment concept) and discourse from a scientific point of view.

Language serves to ensure national unity, increase mass literacy, and promote the development of science and education. Linguistic research cannot be conducted solely within the field of linguistics without taking into account the achievements of other sciences. Filling this gap requires the involvement of fields such as linguoculturology, cognitive linguistics, ethnolinguistics, psycholinguistics, ethnopsycholinguistics, and pragmalinguistics, which are of great importance.

Sociolinguistics also plays a significant role in the integration of language and culture. Although many scientific sources and monographs [1; p. 18; 5; p. 27; 7; p. 101] recognize that sociolinguistics officially developed in the USA, the interaction between language and society, the role of language in culture, national languages and the state language, and views on language policy are also widely observed in Indian, Japanese, German, and Czech linguistics. American linguist V. Bibler puts forward the idea that active sociolinguistic research had already begun in multilingual India in connection with the initiative to make Hindi the only state language [2; p. 91].

In the 1980s, the issue of the social nature of language and the influence of culture on language was discussed in the Uzbek linguistics textbook *Introduction to Linguistics*. However, the problems of language and culture had already been addressed in the works of Jadid scholars such as Fitrat, Elbek, and Botu.

The interconnection between modern countries, peoples, and their cultures is constantly growing and developing. This process has encompassed various spheres of the economic, socio-political, and socio-cultural life of all countries around the world. Nowadays, it is almost impossible to find ethnic communities that are not influenced by the culture of other peoples or by the social environment present in certain regions or globally. This is reflected in the rapid growth of cultural exchange and direct communication between state institutions, social groups, social movements, and individuals.

By becoming participants in any kind of intercultural communication, people often interact with representatives of other cultures. These interactions frequently reveal significant differences, which, in turn, complicate communication. The main reasons for these difficulties lie in differences in mentality and worldviews, that is, in the relationships between peoples of the two societies [5; p. 71]. The solution to this problem is for

people to perceive other cultures through the prism of their own culture. The relevance of all issues related to culture has reached a high level of importance today. The growing interest in studying cultures is evident in the increasing flow of publications on the dialogue between different nations, history, philosophy, philology, and especially on the topic of cultural clashes. These also include societies that bring together researchers of cultural issues.

It should be noted that intercultural communication does not arise spontaneously; rather, it is more effective when studied purposefully as an object of research. It is known that intercultural relations date back to ancient times. Pioneers of intercultural communication such as Alexander the Great, Genghis Khan, Julius Caesar, Christopher Columbus, and others laid the groundwork for the interaction between cultures, the relationship between culture and language, and the search for acceptable forms of intercultural communication [3; p. 104]. This topic continues to be the subject of scientific discussion among researchers.

In local scholarship, the first issues of intercultural communication were addressed by M.V. Lomonosov at the Faculty of Foreign Languages of Moscow State University. It was proven that knowing a foreign language alone is not enough for effective communication with representatives of other cultures [6; p. 2603]. Practice in communicating with foreigners has shown that even deep knowledge of a foreign language does not eliminate misunderstandings and conflicts with native speakers of that language. Therefore, without practical skills in intercultural communication, it is impossible to establish successful and effective interactions with representatives of other cultures.

Compliments are expressed by interlocutors briefly and in a highly polite manner, often in the form of concise statements. They can be delivered directly and plainly or creatively (in an interesting, colorful, meaningful, and multifaceted way).

During the study of the expression of compliments (*mulozamat*), it was found that Germans, in almost all cases, use previously established, standardized forms of compliments, while Uzbeks tend to apply all types of compliments, including multifaceted and unique forms, often creating them spontaneously. In the German mindset, various forms of compliments seem to be fixed, as if they must always be used as ready-made, complex language units [3; p. 49]. Uzbeks, on the other hand, have developed a habit of expressing compliments with great politeness, using various types of exaggeration, metaphors, and newly coined or borrowed words.

If a simple adjective changes its meaning, it then acquires a new valency feature. This new valency realizes a specific construction: *Klarer Himmel* – clear sky. *Er ist großartig*. – He has an open heart.

Sometimes the new valency alters the primary meaning of the adjective and forms a new cognitive structure: *Reicher Mann* – A rich man. *Die Frucht ist reich an das Vitamin* – A fruit rich in vitamins; but: *Die reiche Frucht* does not mean "a fruit rich in vitamins" (in German, it implies something else).

As a result of observations, it was found that adjectives with suffixes, prefixes, and prefix-suffix combinations in the German language are divided into the following lexical-semantic groups (LSG):

- Describing parts of the human body: *bärtiger Mensch* (bearded person), *haarige Beine* (hairy legs), *belebte Männer* (corpulent men), etc.;
- Describing internal emotions, experiences, and states of a person: *gut gelaunter Mann* (good-humored man), *talentierter* (talented).

From the perspective of intercultural communication, and based on the relationship between language and culture, it is possible to distinguish the following research areas:

- Linguistics and regional studies, which primarily have a practical character and serve as valuable sources of information reflecting the interaction between language and culture;
- Ethnolinguistics, which studies the connection between linguistics and ethnicity, closely related to sociolinguistics.

It is worth mentioning the valuable view of the well-known scholar N. Tolstoy regarding the definition of ethnolinguistics: "It is necessary to consider not only the reflection of folk culture, psychology, and mythological ideas in the language but also to take into account the constructive role of language and its impact on the formation and functioning of folk culture, folk psychology, and folk art. The more significant this influence is, the more substantial its indicative level will be."

- Linguoculturology, a field concerned with the problems of the relationship between language and culture and the formation of the linguistic worldview. V.N. Telia defined cultural linguistics as "...a part of ethnolinguistics focused on the synchronous interaction of language and culture, studying and describing their compatibility. Cultural linguistics is studied at the intersection of two fundamental sciences – linguistics and culture" [5; p. 112].

To support our argument, we can point out that the proverbs and idiomatic expressions found in the oral folklore of both the German and Uzbek peoples are rightfully considered the wisdom of the people—cultural experiences preserved in language and passed down from generation to generation. Unlike many other forms, these German-Uzbek proverbs and expressions have not lost their relevance; they are still alive and widely used today.

Proverbs:

1. Auf den Sack schlägt man, den Esel meint man. – "Qizim senga aytaman, kelinim sen eshit." (I'm saying this to my daughter, but I mean it for my daughter-in-law.)
2. Beim Geld hört die Freundschaft auf. – "Pul bolani otadan ayiradi." (Money separates a child from his father.)
3. Allen muss man nicht gefallen. – "Hammaga ham birdek yoqib bo'lmaydi (imkonsiz)." (You can't please everyone.)
4. Alte Freunde und alter Wein sind am besten. – "Libosning yangisi, do'stning eskisi yaxshidir." (New clothes are good, old friends are better.)

Idiomatic Expressions:

1. In Abrahams Schoß sitzen (wie im Paradies leben) – "Xuddi jannatda yashash." (Living like in paradise.)
2. Hinz und Kunz (alle möglichen, x-beliebigen Leute) – "Turfa xil odamlar." (All kinds of people.)
3. Über den großen Onkel gehen (mit einwärts gerichteten Füßen gehen) – "Ichkariga kirmoq." (Walking with inward-turned feet.)
4. Der verlorene Sohn
- (1) "Katta umidsizlikka/tushkunlikka tushmoq." (A great disappointment.)
- (2) "Dom-daraksiz ketgan/yo'qolgan shaxs." (A person who has long disappeared or been unheard of.)

If we pay attention, the fixed expressions or idiomatic phrases from folk oral literature, as well as proverbs, are not translated word for word. Instead, after determining their lexical meaning, their equivalent forms are used. Without a doubt, this phenomenon is not unique to the cultural relationship between German and Uzbek languages but is also reflected in the interaction between different societies, historical layers, and world cultures.

Additionally, legends and myths can serve as an informal method of communication in intercultural dialogue. They often contain invaluable information about the culture of a particular ethnic group and help form a unique perception of its existence [4; p. 19]. Intercultural communication is considered a complex phenomenon studied by many branches of the humanities. Furthermore, this article highlights the historical development of intercultural communication as a distinct area of research.

2 Conclusion

In conclusion, when the linguistic tools under study are used in idiomatic and fixed phrases, their historical-cultural development and uniqueness reveal bright distinctions due to their lack of equivalency. In the linguistic content of intercultural communication between Germans and Uzbeks, the use of set expressions and proverbs demonstrates that, from the perspective of cognitive grammar, the speaker (addresser), in order to convey his or her thoughts to the listener (addressee) accurately and in detail—grammatically, lexically, and semantically—uses not only simple language tools but also complex forms and concepts effectively.

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